

Research Question: To what extent do the algorithmic structures of QuickSort, MergeSort, RadixSort, and BubbleSort affect execution time and memory usage when sorting large datasets of financial transactions in Python 3.13?

Group 4

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1. Introduction

1.1 Rationale

Sorting algorithms are fundamental procedures in Computer Science, and they are used to organize unordered data into an ordered sequence. They are widely used in real-world applications and algorithms, such as sorting prices in the e-commerce platforms from high to low or from low to high, searching functions in the browser, and social media feeds. Therefore, it is essential for a system to find the most appropriate sorting algorithm to optimize the system efficiency and user experience.

During the IB Computer Science HL course, several sorting algorithms have been introduced, such as Bubble Sort and Selection Sort. I was intrigued by the logic and methodologies behind different sorting algorithms, and keen to explore the logic behind different types of sorting algorithms. I have also noticed that the bubble sort and selection sort are often not efficient for large datasets, and different algorithms offer distinct performance in terms of execution time and memory usage. So it is essential to understand the execution time and memory consumption under different situations of each algorithm for a system to operate more efficiently.

Although theoretical complexities learned in high school provide insight into algorithm efficiency, the real-world performance may be different, influenced by implementation, quality of hardware, and the circumstances of the software environment. So, practical testing is important for students to conduct to realize the difference between theory and practice, which also triggers me to understand the trade-off between them.

1.2 Research Question

This essay aims to investigate the following research question:

To what extent do the algorithmic structures of QuickSort, MergeSort, RadixSort, and BubbleSort affect execution time and memory usage when sorting large datasets of financial transactions in Python 3.13?

This investigation will be implemented systematically to evaluate the performance of QuickSort, MergeSort, RadixSort, and BubbleSort by measuring their execution time and memory usage across datasets of different data distribution(sorted order, random order, reverse order) and data size by conducting tests in Python. This empirical approach ensures validity as it involves real-world financial datasets(From Kaggle) and accounts for the hardware interactions and background processes to support comprehensive analysis.

1.3 Hypothesis

Quick Sort will execute fastest in the experiment and with low memory usage on all the datasets due to its divide-and-conquer method. Conversely, Bubble sort is expected to exhibit the slowest execution times, particularly in large datasets, but with low memory usage. The Merge sort and Radix sort are expected to have fast execution time, and with high memory usage compared to Quick sort and Bubble sort, because they are out-of-place sorting algorithms.

2. Background Information

2.1 Sorting Algorithms

Sorting algorithms are computational procedures that permute a sequence of elements into a specific order based on a defined criterion, usually numerical or lexicographic order. These algorithms are the backbone of many computer systems, from database query optimization to user interface improvements. [Eldridge, 2025]

2.2 Time complexity of a sorting algorithm

Time complexity quantifies the relationship between an algorithm's runtime and the size of the input (n); it is necessary to isolate the algorithm's efficiency from external factors, such as background processes. In computer science, employing the asymptotic notation to represent the time complexity:

Types of Complexity Bounds[Nandhini P, 2024]:

1. Omega Notation(Ω): When the sorting algorithm takes the minimal amount of time to reorder, which is the lower bound, typically when the list is already sorted.
2. Theta notation(Θ): When the algorithm is executed on a randomly ordered input of size n , it is the tight bound.
3. Big O notation(O): When the algorithm is executed on an input of size n , and it requires the maximum amount of time to finish the process, which is the upper bound.

Mathematical Definition of Big O: “Given two functions $f(n)$ and $g(n)$, we say that $f(n) = O(g(n))$ if there exist constants $c > 0$ and $n_0 \geq 0$ such that: $f(n) \leq c \cdot g(n)$ for all $n \geq n_0$ ”

[geeksforgeeks, 2025]

Figure 1: Comparison of Different Time Complexity Growth Rates (Kelvin, 2019)

2.3 Space complexity

Space complexity measures the relationship between input size n and the memory usage to eliminate the influence of hardware configuration and software circumstances. For this investigation, the focus is on the auxiliary space complexity, only the extra memory allocated, excluding the space taken by the data itself[Nandhini P, 2024].

- In place: does not require extra auxiliary memory.
- Out-of-place: requires extra auxiliary memory and varies by algorithms, $O(n)$.

2.4 In-place Algorithm

Refers to the algorithm that transforms the input data structure without requiring a significant amount of auxiliary memory. It operates directly on the input array with a small amount of extra memory, and is usually $O(1)$ for temporary variables used during operations. **In this investigation, Bubble sort and Quick sort are both in-place algorithms**(Pooja, 2024).

Advantage:

1. Memory-efficient:

A small constant amount of extra auxiliary memory is used, and the memory consumption remains constant when the size of the input list increases.

2. Spatial Locality:

An in-place algorithm often processes elements that are adjacent in the memory. This maximizes the CPU cache hit, thereby reducing the latency caused by fetching data from RAM.

Disadvantages:

1. Algorithm instability:

Many of the In-place algorithms do not preserve the relative order of elements with equal keys(duplicate values).

2. Destructive modification:

In-place algorithm directly executes swapping operations in the input list structure, which means a manual copy should be created before each sorting if the unordered version data needs to be maintained. [Singh, 2025]

Figure 2: Example of a stable sort and an unstable sort (Priyank, 2022)

2.5 Out-of-place algorithm

An out-of-place algorithm uses a large amount of auxiliary memory to execute. It creates new data structures(temporary array or list) to help the process of sorting. **Merge sort and Radix sort are both out-of-place algorithms in this experiment.** (Educative, 2025)

Advantages:

Non-destructive:

Out-of-place algorithms allow for non-destructive sorting more easily, which means the original input data remains intact; a manual hardcopy is not mandatory before each execution.

Stability:

Out-of-place algorithm usually provides a stable sorting logic when using auxiliary storage; As seen in Figure 2, the relative order of duplicate values is automatically preserved.

Disadvantages:

Memory-intensive:

out-of-place algorithms require a significant amount of auxiliary memory to create subarrays and to sort the input data. For a large database(E.g, N = 100000+), it can trigger the system to use a hard disk as temporary storage(virtual memory), which drastically delays the execution speed.

Allocation Overhead:

The system requires CPU cycles to allocate and deallocate the memory blocks; it needs extra time to execute this process compared to in-place sorting algorithms. [Engineering a Compiler, 2012]

2.6 Bubble Sort (Naive vs Optimized)

Bubble sort is a fundamental, comparison-based sorting algorithm that repeatedly steps through the input list element by element, compares the adjacent elements, and swaps the elements if they are in the wrong order. [GeeksforGeeks, 2014]

Figure 2: Demonstration of how bubble sort works

(ProductPlan, 2020)

Optimization:

A standardized “naive” Bubble sort’s time complexity is always $O(N^2)$. The optimized version(implemented in this research for comparison) utilises a swapped flag. If no swaps occur during a pass, the algorithm finishes early, allowing $O(n)$ performance on the sorted input list.

Theoretical Time Complexity:

Worst-case time complexity	$O(N^2)$
Average-case time complexity	$O(N^2)$
Best-case time complexity	$O(N)$, but $O(N^2)$ for the

	naive version.
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[Alake, 2023]

Memory Complexity:

Worst-case space Complexity	$O(1)$
Average-case space complexity	$O(1)$
Best-case space Complexity	$O(1)$

Critical Analysis:

Comparing both versions calculates the computational cost of redundancy. This comparison can demonstrate that logic optimization can significantly improve the best-case performance.

2.7 Divide-and-conquer algorithm

The divide-and-conquer algorithm is often used to find the optimal solution by decomposing a given problem into two or more similar and simpler subgroups [GeeksforGeeks, 2012]. After the divide process, the system conquers the sub-problems. Ultimately, we collect solutions to the sub-problems to solve the original problem. In this experiment, **Quick sort and Merge sort** are both divide-and-conquer algorithms.

Figure 3: Demonstration of how the divide and conquer algorithm works

(Ayaan Alam, 2012)

2.8 QuickSort

QuickSort is a type of divide-and-conquer algorithm that selects a pivot element each time, then partitions the array into sub-arrays based on the pivot, and recursively sorts the partitions.

Figure 4: Demonstration of how quicksort works

(GeeksforGeeks, 2025)

Time complexity:

Best case	$\Omega(n \log n)$
Average Case	$\theta(n \log n)$
Worst Case	$O(n^2)$

Space complexity:

Best case	$\Omega(\log n)$
Average case	$\theta(\log n)$

Worst case	$O(n)$
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Note, if the quick sort is using randomized pivot selection, it can significantly eliminate the chance to get worst cases, which is the optimized version.

Critical Analysis:

Quick Sort represents the industry standard for general sorting purposes due to its spatial locality and high performance. However, a poor pivot choice can lead to unstable performance($O(n^2)$). This investigation explores whether the theoretical risk(unstable performance) outweighs its benefits, such as low constant factors and cache efficiency.

2.9 MergeSort

MergeSort is a type of divide-and-conquer algorithm that recursively divides the list into halves, sorts each half, and then merges them.

Figure 3

[2025, Geeksforgeeks]

Time complexity:

Best case	$\Omega(n \log n)$
Average case	$\Theta(n \log n)$
Worst Case	$O(n \log n)$

Auxiliary space:

Best Case	$\Omega(n)$
Average Case	$\Theta(n)$
Worst Case	$O(n)$

Critical analysis:

The primary trade-off analyzed here is the memory allocation overhead. It requires $O(n)$ auxiliary space, compared to an in-place algorithm.

2.10 Radix sort:

Radix sort is a linear sorting, non-comparative algorithm that sorts elements by processing them digit by digit. (2025, Geeksforgeeks)

Figure 4

[Programiz, n.d.]

Time Complexity

Best case	$\Omega(n*d)$
Average case	$\Theta(n*d)$
Worst Case	$O(n*d)$

Auxiliary space:

Best Case	$\Omega(n + k)$
Average Case	$\Theta(n + k)$
Worst Case	$O(n + k)$

Critical Analysis:

It is the only non-comparative sorting algorithm. This investigation evaluates the trade-off between the reduced CPU comparisons and the high memory bandwidth required for bucket operations, which can degrade the performance due to poor memory locality.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This investigation follows an empirical experimental process to compare the algorithm performance in terms of time and space complexity for BubbleSort, QuickSort, RadixSort, and MergeSort. In this experiment, A real-world dataset containing financial integers will be utilized by splitting into different sizes and degrees of entropy. This experiment will measure both time taken and space consumption for each algorithm across data of increasing size and entropy, and each test will be repeated 5 times to reduce the impact of confounding variables. The average value will be calculated at the end, plotted in the graph, and compared with the theory.

3.2 variables

Independent variable:

Input size (n) — the number of values being sorted. (Range from 2000 to 10000, step 2000).

Algorithm types — distinct sorting algorithms are applied to the same-sized dataset to compare efficiency.

Data entropy — the input data is generated in three specific configurations, in this experiment, including sorted, random, and reversed scenarios.

Dependent variable:

Execution time(s) — measured by using the `perf_counter()` function, providing a high precision to capture the runtime of an algorithm.

Peak memory(MiB) — Measured using the `memory_profiler` library, which can track the maximum memory usage during the sorting process.

Controlled variable:

Hardware configuration:

All the tests are conducted by the same hardware configuration in this experiment to ensure the internal validity. It is because the algorithm's performance is highly affected by the RAM read/write speeds and CPU efficiency. Using the same hardware can significantly minimize the hardware bias to get accurate results.

Software environment:

In this research project, the same version of Python Interpreter (3.13) and software (PyCharm Community Edition 2024.2.1) will be used to conduct all the experiments to maintain a consistent and controlled software environment. The software environment is a necessary factor to control, it is because different versions of Python may have optimizations or overhead that impact performance. Keeping a constant software environment ensures consistency in measurements and precise results.

Algorithm implementation:

In each test for the same algorithm, the sorting algorithm must be implemented using the same code to ensure internal validity. It is necessary to control because different versions of the same sorting algorithm will affect the execution time and memory usage.

Background processes

Modern operating system uses CPU scheduling and context switching to manage active tasks[GeekforGeeks, 2023]. If the background process causes more CPU usage during the test, it can cause an outlier. Before each test, all unnecessary applications and browser tabs should be closed to minimize Interference. It is important to acknowledge that background processes can not be eliminated, but these steps can increase the reliability of the measurements.

3.3 Dataset

The Huge Stock Market Dataset is from Kaggle, which provides the full historical daily price and volume data for all US-based stocks up to 11/10/2017. This secondary dataset is suitable for this experiment due to its big scale (492MB) and real historical data. This investigation specifically utilizes the volume column, as it contains a large number of numerical values. Python script will be used to support isolating numerical values and creating controlled samples of varying record sizes (e.g, 2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000). These samples will be sorted under different initial orderings, including reversed, random, and sorted, to analyze the time and space complexity of different algorithms.

3.4 Experiment setup and procedure

To address the research question, a structured experiment should be conducted to measure the average time:

1. Environment Preparation: Before the test run, an identical laptop will be used (mine: Microsoft Windows 11 Home). Unnecessary applications and browser tabs need to be closed. All tests are conducted in PyCharm Community Edition 2024.2.1 with Python Interpreter 3.13.0.

2. Data Loading and Sample creation: A Python script will be used to load the volume column from the Kaggle stock market datasets by using the Pandas, os, json, and random modules. For each test size (2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000), there are three versions of the sample created: one randomly shuffled by directly copying the data from the dataset. One is sorted by using the `sorted()` function, and one is reversely sorted by using the `sorted(sample_data, reverse = True)` function. This allows us to test the various data conditions for different sorting algorithms to gain a more comprehensive understanding. All the necessary data will be created before each experiment.

3. Algorithm implementation: Standard Python implementations of Bubble sort (Naive and Optimized), Radix sort, merge sort, and Quick sort will be implemented.

4. Performance measurement (two phases, and are conducted in different time):

- **Execution time:** the time module will be imported and time. The `perf_counter` function records the start and end time of each algorithm.

Calculation:

$$Runtime = t_{end} - t_{start}$$

- **Memory usage:** The `@profile` decorator from the `memory_profiler` library can track the memory consumption of each sorting algorithm effectively.

5. Repeat experiment and get average: Repeat each test 5 times for each unique combination of algorithm, sample size, and data condition. The average time and memory usage will be calculated for each trial. Finally, the averages will be plotted with the sample size to analyze the growth rate and compare with the theoretical performance.

4. Experimental Data:

The following diagram displays the time complexity and memory complexity of different sorting algorithms for different data sizes. All processed graphs were generated by Google Sheets or PyCharm.

4.1 Time Complexity Result Data of Bubble Sort:

Time complexity data for naive Bubble Sort and optimized Bubble Sort:

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (s)	Trial 2 (s)	Trial 3 (s)	Trial 4 (s)	Trial 5 (s)	Average (s)
2000	Random	0.213641	0.272622	0.214929	0.210698	0.21042	0.224462
	Sorted	0.131368	0.135003	0.121595	0.124544	0.124288	0.12736
	Reversed	0.289959	0.256019	0.287007	0.28367	0.285609	0.280453
4000	Random	0.867085	0.85662	0.98129	0.930499	0.88435	0.903969
	Sorted	0.52937	0.51634	0.515804	0.529897	0.532281	0.524738
	Reversed	1.156974	1.168209	1.125848	1.23067	1.221236	1.180587
6000	Random	2.02325	2.045928	2.179608	2.065393	2.107187	2.084273
	Sorted	1.342201	1.406457	1.414911	1.563512	1.692702	1.483957
	Reversed	2.92846	2.916751	3.028636	2.818105	3.1545	2.96929
8000	Random	3.918883	3.488931	4.450296	5.516564	3.291166	4.133168
	Sorted	1.994809	1.981562	2.004104	1.984164	1.974776	1.987883
	Reversed	4.469164	4.410617	4.322843	4.270308	4.323262	4.359239
10000	Random	5.224953	5.115429	5.128101	5.095186	5.104547	5.133643
	Sorted	3.719108	3.1204	3.251138	3.174242	3.087733	3.270524
	Reversed	6.784567	7.501227	6.969832	7.226503	7.18794	7.134014

Figure 5: Raw Execution Time (s) for Naive Bubble Sort across Random, Sorted, and Reversed Datasets

n	Input Type	Avg Time (s)	Best Case	Worst Case
2000	Sorted	0.000126	0.000121	0.000133
	Random	0.2347	0.225	0.247
	Reversed	0.3108	0.296	0.338
4000	Sorted	0.000271	0.000266	0.000277
	Random	1.0265	0.961	1.068
	Reversed	1.2272	1.069	1.312
6000	Sorted	0.00049	0.000376	0.000663
	Random	1.8429	1.786	1.911
	Reversed	2.5776	2.37	3.232
8000	Sorted	0.000403	0.000393	0.000437
	Random	3.4472	3.289	3.633
	Reversed	4.4751	4.33	4.731
10000	Sorted	0.000549	0.000443	0.000729
	Random	5.9452	5.226	6.983
	Reversed	7.2078	7.12	7.306

Figure 6: Raw Execution Time (s) for Optimized Bubble Sort across Random, Sorted, and Reversed Datasets

Bubble Sort (Naive) Time Complexity - $O(n^2)$ Input-Dependent Performance

Figure 7: Growth Rate of Execution Time for Naive Bubble Sort Compared to Theory

Optimized Bubble Sort - I/O Isolated Analysis

Figure 8: Growth Rate of Execution Time for Optimized Bubble Sort Compared to Theory

4.2 Space Complexity Result Data of Bubble Sort

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (B)	Trial 2 (B)	Trial 3 (B)	Trial 4 (B)	Trial 5 (B)	Peak Avg (B)	Extra Memory (B)
2000	Random	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Sorted	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Reversed	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
4000	Random	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Sorted	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Reversed	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
6000	Random	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Sorted	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Reversed	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
8000	Random	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Sorted	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Reversed	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
10000	Random	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Sorted	268	268	268	268	268	268	268
	Reversed	268	268	268	268	268	268	268

Figure 9: Peak Auxiliary Memory Usage (Bytes) for Naive Bubble Sort.

Size (n)	Input Type	Initial Memory	Peak Memory	Extra Memory (Peak - Initial)
2000	Random	16,000	16,268	268
	Sorted	16,000	16,268	268
	Reversed	16,000	16,268	268
4000	Random	32,000	32,268	268
	Sorted	32,000	32,268	268
	Reversed	32,000	32,268	268
6000	Random	48,000	48,268	268
	Sorted	48,000	48,268	268
	Reversed	48,000	48,268	268
8000	Random	64,000	64,268	268
	Sorted	64,000	64,268	268
	Reversed	64,000	64,268	268
10000	Random	80,000	80,268	268
	Sorted	80,000	80,268	268
	Reversed	80,000	80,268	268

Figure 10: Peak Auxiliary Memory Usage (Bytes) for Optimized Bubble Sort.

Processed Bubble sort memory usage graphs:

Figure 11: Space Complexity of a Naive Bubble Sort across increasing Input Sizes (n)

Figure 12: Space Complexity of an Optimized Bubble Sort across increasing Input Sizes (n)

4.3 Result data of Quick Sort (optimized version):

The quick sort uses randomized pivot selection to significantly reduce the chance that the worst-case time complexity occurs.

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (s)	Trial 2 (s)	Trial 3 (s)	Trial 4 (s)	Trial 5 (s)	Average (s)
2000	Random	0.028735	0.029804	0.030962	0.029664	0.029817	0.029796
	Sorted	0.028925	0.031301	0.03335	0.029922	0.029128	0.030525
	Reversed	0.02823	0.030012	0.030765	0.030484	0.02891	0.02968
4000	Random	0.068596	0.070587	0.064561	0.067614	0.064934	0.067258
	Sorted	0.060753	0.059956	0.061852	0.067684	0.065081	0.063065
	Reversed	0.060146	0.060855	0.062588	0.070215	0.064975	0.063756
6000	Random	0.095365	0.095834	0.128972	0.102817	0.098828	0.104363
	Sorted	0.093525	0.096536	0.106436	0.095434	0.096924	0.097771
	Reversed	0.096953	0.096298	0.105193	0.09523	0.093992	0.097533
8000	Random	0.134524	0.139869	0.135085	0.132549	0.141408	0.136687
	Sorted	0.136193	0.170502	0.152567	0.160661	0.138567	0.151698
	Reversed	0.134746	0.140318	0.134216	0.160861	0.159955	0.146019
10000	Random	0.206781	0.198277	0.176129	0.170497	0.177243	0.185785
	Sorted	0.176166	0.188197	0.174397	0.171196	0.172893	0.17657
	Reversed	0.174006	0.181827	0.171432	0.174798	0.172207	0.174854

Figure 13: Execution Time of Optimized QuickSort with Randomized Pivot Selection across different Data Distributions.

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (B)	Trial 2 (B)	Trial 3 (B)	Trial 4 (B)	Trial 5 (B)	Peak Avg (B)	Extra Memory (B)
2000	Random	1,712	1,728	1,536	1600	1792	1673.6	~1674
	Sorted	1,840	1,600	1,536	1392	1536	1580.8	~1581
	Reversed	1,584	1,520	1,456	1584	1648	1558.4	~1558
4000	Random	1,792	1,776	1,792	1792	2048	1840	~1840
	Sorted	1,728	1,968	1,728	2240	1792	1891.2	~1891
	Reversed	1,904	1,712	2,224	1600	1728	1833.6	~1834
6000	Random	1,664	1,904	1,792	1984	1712	1811.2	~1811
	Sorted	1,984	1,984	2,096	1792	1856	1942.4	~1942
	Reversed	1,920	1,856	1,904	1920	1904	1900.8	~1901
8000	Random	1,840	1,984	2,032	2288	1920	2012.8	~2013
	Sorted	2,032	1,856	1,904	1856	2288	1987.2	~1987
	Reversed	2,048	2,112	1,920	2112	1920	2022.4	~2022
10000	Random	1,920	2,160	1,920	1856	2288	2028.8	~2029
	Sorted	2,288	1,856	2,112	2096	1968	2064	~2064
	Reversed	2,176	2,176	1,984	2176	2112	2124.8	~2125

Figure 14: Memory Consumption of Optimized QuickSort with Randomized Pivot Selection across different Data Distributions.

Processed graphs for Quick Sort:

Figure 15: Growth Rate of Execution Time for Quick Sort Compared to Theory

Random Avg (B), Sorted Avg (B) and Reversed Avg (B)

Figure 16: Space Complexity of a Quick Sort across increasing Input Sizes (n)

4.4 Result data of Merge Sort:

Input Type	n (Size)	Trial 1 (s)	Trial 2 (s)	Trial 3 (s)	Trial 4 (s)	Trial 5 (s)	Average (s)
Random	2000	0.0066852	0.0078772	0.0059674	0.0065108	0.0060346	0.0066150
Sorted		0.0056372	0.0072192	0.0066180	0.0058584	0.0062112	0.0063088
Reversed		0.0057322	0.0062632	0.0061078	0.0059434	0.0060694	0.0060232
Random	4000	0.0163138	0.0170362	0.0120740	0.0133618	0.0134910	0.0144554
Sorted		0.0133028	0.0140826	0.0123764	0.0159594	0.0123966	0.0136236
Reversed		0.0132032	0.0133444	0.0119610	0.0159894	0.0136372	0.0136270
Random	6000	0.0205250	0.0219460	0.0238612	0.0213476	0.0210082	0.0217376
Sorted		0.0197040	0.0209462	0.0217130	0.0192506	0.0194582	0.0202144
Reversed		0.0203646	0.0191900	0.0226094	0.0242494	0.0239600	0.0220746
Random	8000	0.0366282	0.0377138	0.0347688	0.0343484	0.0340554	0.0355030
Sorted		0.0345374	0.0394748	0.0399604	0.0323162	0.0299050	0.0352388
Reversed		0.0327738	0.0375724	0.0354642	0.0314406	0.0334394	0.0341380
Random	10000	0.0495228	0.0452640	0.0478116	0.0392306	0.0342916	0.0432242
Sorted		0.0354550	0.0396732	0.0358226	0.0353666	0.0362168	0.0365068
Reversed		0.0377084	0.0404042	0.0345960	0.0337938	0.0364316	0.0365868

Figure 17: Raw Execution Time (s) for Merge Sort across Random, Sorted, and Reversed Datasets

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (B)	Trial 2 (B)	Trial 3 (B)	Trial 4 (B)	Trial 5 (B)	Peak Avg (B)	Extra Memory (B)
2000	Random	16,288	16,288	16,288	16288	16288	16288	16288
	Sorted	16,288	16,288	16,288	16288	16288	16288	16288
	Reversed	16,288	16,288	16,288	16288	16288	16288	16288
4000	Random	32,272	32,272	32,272	32272	32272	32272	32272
	Sorted	32,272	32,272	32,272	32272	32272	32272	32272
	Reversed	32,272	32,272	32,272	32272	32272	32272	32272
6000	Random	48,280	48,280	48,280	48280	48280	48280	48280
	Sorted	48,280	48,280	48,280	48280	48280	48280	48280
	Reversed	48,280	48,280	48,280	48280	48280	48280	48280
8000	Random	64,288	64,288	64,288	64288	64288	64288	64288
	Sorted	64,288	64,288	64,288	64288	64288	64288	64288
	Reversed	64,288	64,288	64,288	64288	64288	64288	64288
10000	Random	80,280	80,280	80,280	80280	80280	80280	80280
	Sorted	80,280	80,280	80,280	80280	80280	80280	80280
	Reversed	80,280	80,280	80,280	80280	80280	80280	80280

Figure 18: Memory Consumption of Merge sort across Random, Sorted, and Reversed Datasets.

Merge sort processed graphs:

Figure 19: Growth Rate of Execution Time for Merge Sort Compared to Theory

Figure 20: Space Complexity of a Merge Sort across increasing Input Sizes (n)

4.5 Result data of Radix Sort:

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (s)	Trial 2 (s)	Trial 3 (s)	Trial 4 (s)	Trial 5 (s)	Average (s)
2000	Random	0.006379	0.006403	0.006599	0.006266	0.006231	0.006376
	Sorted	0.005993	0.005941	0.006347	0.005031	0.004227	0.005508
	Reversed	0.005597	0.006234	0.005862	0.006389	0.006086	0.006034
4000	Random	0.01164	0.013575	0.009043	0.012544	0.012857	0.011932
	Sorted	0.01508	0.014963	0.009223	0.012636	0.015105	0.013401
	Reversed	0.01356	0.014623	0.015766	0.012607	0.014334	0.014178
6000	Random	0.023065	0.019739	0.019459	0.019319	0.015076	0.019332
	Sorted	0.014582	0.014682	0.019604	0.022579	0.023993	0.019088
	Reversed	0.022051	0.020567	0.019028	0.015576	0.019542	0.019353
8000	Random	0.031429	0.028737	0.028726	0.028971	0.033631	0.030299
	Sorted	0.034355	0.035014	0.032894	0.030885	0.020978	0.030825
	Reversed	0.030135	0.031956	0.032765	0.030981	0.03144	0.031455
10000	Random	0.027161	0.03274	0.03577	0.033035	0.033377	0.032417
	Sorted	0.03278	0.034123	0.040139	0.036751	0.033769	0.035512
	Reversed	0.030775	0.02993	0.031351	0.033011	0.027265	0.030466

Figure 21: Raw Execution Time (s) for Radix Sort across Random, Sorted, and Reversed Datasets

n (Size)	Input Type	Trial 1 (B)	Trial 2 (B)	Trial 3 (B)	Trial 4 (B)	Trial 5 (B)	Peak Avg (B)	Extra Memory (B)
2000	Random	16,568	16,568	16,568	16568	16568	16568	16568
	Sorted	16,568	16,568	16,568	16568	16568	16568	16568
	Reversed	16,568	16,568	16,568	16568	16568	16568	16568
4000	Random	32,588	32,588	32,588	32588	32588	32588	32588
	Sorted	32,588	32,588	32,588	32588	32588	32588	32588
	Reversed	32,588	32,588	32,588	32588	32588	32588	32588
6000	Random	48,596	48,596	48,596	48596	48596	48596	48596
	Sorted	48,596	48,596	48,596	48596	48596	48596	48596
	Reversed	48,592	48,592	48,592	48592	48592	48592	48592
8000	Random	64,604	64,604	64,604	64604	64604	64604	64604
	Sorted	64,604	64,604	64,604	64604	64604	64604	64604
	Reversed	64,604	64,604	64,604	64604	64604	64604	64604
10000	Random	80,596	80,596	80,596	80596	80596	80596	80596
	Sorted	80,596	80,596	80,596	80596	80596	80596	80596
	Reversed	80,596	80,596	80,596	80596	80596	80596	80596

Figure 22: Memory Consumption for Radix Sort across Random, Sorted, and Reversed Datasets

Processed graph for radix sort:

Figure 23: Growth Rate of Execution Time for Radix Sort Compared to Theory

Figure 24: Space Complexity of a Radix Sort across increasing Input Sizes (n)

5. Data analysis:

This chapter will comprehensively interpret the data collected from the experiment, finding the potential anomalies and the underlying trends and meanings from the collected data. This analysis also correlates the practical data with the theoretical computational complexity.

5.1 Bubble Sort(Naive vs Optimized)

I mainly explore the performance between the naive Bubble Sort and the optimized Bubble Sort. As shown in the figure 5 and 6, the results of the random and reverse cases are nearly identical, but the sorted case has a relatively huge difference, e.g., the naive bubble sort took 3.270524(s) to sort a file of 10000 integers, but the optimized bubble sort only takes 0.000549(s), which is around 5958 × speedup. This evidence supports the theoretical best-case complexity of $O(n)$ mentioned in Alake(2023), because the optimized version includes a swapped flag for early termination(in the Appendix, Optimized Bubble Sort). In Figures 7 and 8, the data are nearly aligned with the theory, and in both naive and optimized bubble sort graphs, the reverse data cases nearly show $O(n^2)$ (quadratic) time complexity. Overall, the execution time of Bubble sort is relatively slow compared to other algorithms.

Average Execution Time (s) for Naive vs. Optimized Bubble Sort				
n (Size)	Input Type	Naive Sort Avg Time (s)*	Optimized Sort Avg Time (s)	Speedup Factor
2000	Random	0.224	0.234	~1x
2000	Sorted	0.127	0.000126	~1000x
2000	Reversed	0.28	0.31	~1x
10000	Random	5.133	5.945	~1x
10000	Sorted	3.271	0.000549	~5958x
10000	Reversed	7.134	7.207	~1x

Figure 25: Comparisons of Average Execution Time(s) between naive and optimized versions of Bubble Sort.

In terms of the space complexity of bubble sort, the naive and optimized algorithms both demonstrate $O(1)$, as shown in the GeeksforGeeks (2014), showing that bubble sort is memory-efficient.

Conclusion: This experiment's results directly showcase that bubble sort is a memory-efficient but relatively slow sorting algorithm, which mostly aligns with my hypothesis.

5.2 Quick Sort

As seen in Figures 15 and 16, the experimental data for Quick Sort demonstrate and confirm that the optimized Quick Sort exhibits robust $O(n \log n)$ time complexity and $O(1)$ auxiliary space complexity across random, sorted, and reverse data structures. The time complexity graph(Figure 15) shows that all the lines have a high similarity to the $O(n \log n)$ graph. The uniform performance across all the data types is because of randomized pivot selection, which effectively prevents the unoptimized quicksort worst-case $O(n^2)$ scenario. Figure 16 shows that it spends nearly the same amount of extra memory to sort different sizes and types of data(a little discrepancy is because each recursive call adds new frames to the stack), but still proves it is memory efficient. While GeekforGeeks (2018) notes “Quicksort exhibits good cache locality and this makes quicksort faster than merge sort”, but in my experiment results as shown from figures 13, 17, and 21, Quick Sort takes 5 times more to sort data compared to merge sort and radix sort, and this is likely due to the high computational overhead of Python’s `random.randint` function and Python’s manual element swapping `arr[pivot_index], arr[high] = arr[high], arr[pivot_index]`. (Quick Sort Time Complexity code in Appendix)

Conclusion: the optimized quick sort algorithm shows a tradeoff in computer science, it provides consistent execution time and prevent worst-case from happening, but also takes a longer time to process due to random pivot selection. However, the time complexity and space complexity mostly align with the experiment.

5.3 Merge Sort

The experimental results of the merge sort algorithm (figure 19, figure 20) strongly suggest that it matches the theoretical time and space complexity. In Figure 19, different data types line up with the $O(n \log n)$ log-linear time complexity, and each line shows $O(n \log n)$ under different data distribution conditions, which is a main strength of merge sort. The divide and conquer approach ensures the execution time performance is similar across best, average, and worst cases because the number of comparisons and merge operations remains nearly constant regardless of the initial input size. The space complexity in my merge sort algorithm test result is perfectly linear $O(n)$, as we can see in Figure 18. When $n=2000$, the file size is approximately 16 KB; when $n=10000$, the file size is approximately 80 KB. These data confirm that the Merge sort disadvantage: it needs additional memory for storing, as shown in GeekforGeeks(2013).

Conclusion: The merge sort is a stable algorithm with efficient time usage to sort data. The divide and conquer method also causes the use of extra memory, although it is less memory efficient than in-place sorting algorithms, such as quick sort and bubble sort, but it provides a more stable performance than others, which mostly aligns with my hypothesis.

5.4 Performance Analysis of Radix Sort

The experiment result of Radix Sort clearly show efficiency in execution time, but consume too much memory, aligning with the non-comparison-based sorting algorithm theory. In the processed graph(Figure 23), the time execution experiment data is similar to $O(n)$ linear time complexity. A linear regression analysis shows that $R^2 = 0.968$, which shows a high degree of correlation. The data demonstrates a stable performance, where doubling the input size n results in approximately doubling the execution time. And also In Figure 23, the best, average, and worst cases of different sizes are highly similar, also indicating the stability of its performance. (This speed is due to the digit-wise sorting mechanism of radix sort, which bypasses the $O(n \log n)$ time complexity limitation of comparison-based algorithms such as merge sort or quicksort. The results show no significant difference with random, sorted, and reversed inputs, proving that the algorithm is independent of initial order.) In Figure 24, the graph reveals $O(n)$ linear space complexity; memory usage directly increases when the input size increases, from approximately 16.6 KB when $n=2000$ to approximately 80.6 KB when $n=10000$, which indicates it needs a large amount of auxiliary memory to assist in sorting, and may cause a burden to the hardware when sorting a large amount of data.

6. Conclusion

This investigation aims to answer the question “To what extent do the algorithmic structures of QuickSort, MergeSort, RadixSort, and BubbleSort affect execution time and memory usage when sorting large datasets of financial transactions in Python 3.13? ” And the method is to implement rigorous experiments with standard approaches to measure the time execution and memory consumption of real-world datasets across 2000 - 10000 to analyze specifically four different sorting algorithms, including BubbleSort, RadixSort, MergeSort, and QuickSort, to provide various raw data and processed graphs. The choice of the sorting algorithm, input size, and data distribution can definitely have a big impact on the time efficiency and memory consumption. The experimental result clearly shows the difference between the in-place algorithm and the out-of-place algorithm[Figure 11, Figure 16, Figure 20, and Figure 24], and the discrepancy between the real-world implementation and the theories. Such as the experiment results for the QuickSort, its sorting speed is 5 times slower than MergeSort due to manual element swapping and the extra memory usage of the QuickSort[Figure 16] is not absolute 0, it is slightly increased when the size of the data is increased, this is due to recursive call also create frame to store local variables, when the size is big, the system likely to create more frames to store variables.

Regarding to the research question, the algorithmic structure does significantly affect the execution time and memory usage, as shown in the experiments, some types of sorting algorithms have excellent and stable performance in time execution but need to use a relatively large amount of auxiliary array, such as Merge sort and Radix sort, which both need to spend around 80000 bytes to sort a 10000 integer list. In the meantime, in-place algorithms such as Bubble sort and quicksort are efficient in terms of memory consumption, but Bubble sort lacks efficiency in time execution; quicksort has relatively excellent performance in both memory consumption and time execution. The size of the datasets can also affect the performance significantly. A common trend for every tested algorithm is

that when the size of the dataset is increased, the execution time is also always increased, and the memory consumption depends on the type of the algorithm. In-place algorithms, such as bubble sort, have the same memory usage across all sizes, as they directly do comparisons and swaps to the dataset. These experiments mostly confirm the theoretical complexities, and they have a high reliability by using systematic measuring methods.

7. Evaluation:

In this research project, my research effectively reveals that the input size, data distribution, and sort algorithm can impact the performance of a sorting algorithm's time execution and memory usage. This research project utilized two Python-built-in modules `timeit`, and `tracemalloc`, to measure the time execution and memory consumption across different types of sorting algorithms on real-world datasets, stock market ($n=2k-1M$), results highly confirmed with the theoretical time complexity, such as Radix Sort achieved $O(n)$ ($R^2=0.968$, figure 23), QuickSort $O(n \log n)$ ($R^2>0.97$, figure 15).

Strengths of this report can include implementing real-world datasets, a large volume of data, and selected sorting algorithms that are quite distinct in sorting principles and methodologies.

Weaknesses include that experimental errors still exist and are not well-controlled in the experiment due to confounding variables, such as background processes, minor mistakes in the code implementation, the number of sorting algorithms, and the testing size is also limited.

Improvements include using more standardized testing methods and a professional configuration to test the experiment results. Also, A wider range of data size (n) and sorting algorithms, and more professional devices need to be involved in the experiment to provide a professional analysis.

8. Bibliography

Notice:

I used Gemini AI and Grammarly to correct my spelling, find more appropriate words, and correct grammar. (Please check the records of AI usage in the Appendix)

2. Essay structure followed the format on Clastify website:

<https://www.clastify.com/blog/computer-science-ee-format-and-structure>

3. Gemini AI was also used to provide recommendations in terms of brainstorming, writing more academically and formally, helping with word choice, and giving feedback.

https://gemini.google.com/app?utm_source=ai.google&utm_medium=referral

4. DeepL translator is also used to assist reading.

<https://www.deepl.com/en>

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Appendix:

Records of AI usage in this EE

Phase of EE	AI Tool	How it was used
Introduction	Gemini AI	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Ask for suggestions on some appropriate research questions that are not really complicated.2. Ask for appropriate sources that can help me to write the EE, such as the EE format on Clastify.3. After finding out that it is better to use a real-world dataset for testing, I asked Gemini AI where I can find real-world datasets.4. Checking whether my first draft of the introduction matches the format in Clastify, and asking for feedback.
Background Information	Gemini AI	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Ask what to write in the background information parts.2. After finishing the background Information, I sent my draft to the AI, and let it be based on the format in the Clastify to give recommendations. It recommended me to add images and critical analysis parts for each sorting algorithm.
Methodology	Gemini AI	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. After finishing the first draft, I asked AI if I lacked some of the important variables.2. After finishing the procedures of the experiment, I asked AI if my approach to the procedures was appropriate. I checked the feedback, and adopted some parts, such as using the <code>perf_counter</code> function and <code>use</code> function from the <code>memory_profiler</code> library.
Data Analysis	Gemini AI	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. After finishing the draft, I sent it to AI to ask for recommendations, and I got feedback that I need to be more analytical, instead of just describing the data, but illustrating why the data is like that.

Coding	Gemini AI	I used it for debugging(when I really can not find the bug), and asked for feedbacks if my code is appropriate.
Review	Gemini AI	I used it for correcting Grammar and Speling, and also asked for some recommendations for word choice, such as the entropy in the background information.

The following code was used for this investigation.

Bubble sort naive time complexity:

```
import json
import timeit

#=====Creating a optimized bubble sort
algorithm=====
def bubble_sort(arr):
    n = len(arr)
    for i in range(n - 1):
        for j in range(0, n - i - 1):
            if arr[j] > arr[j + 1]:
                arr[j], arr[j + 1] = arr[j + 1], arr[j]
    return arr

def run_sort(new_data):
    processed_data = list(new_data)
    bubble_sort(processed_data)

#=====
sample_size = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Creating a two dimensional loop for data
testing=====
for size in sample_size:
```

```

for sample_type in sample_types:
    filename = f"Sorting samplesample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
    print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine whether the system is executing
#=====Opening the json file=====
    with open(filename, 'r') as f:
        data = json.load(f)

    new_data = []
    for x in data:
        try:
            new_data.append(int(x))
        except ValueError:
            pass # Do ignore non-value error...
#=====Final testing and displaying the result
    times = timeit.repeat( # timeit.repeat() runs the same code multiple times and
returns execution times
        stmt=lambda: run_sort(new_data),
        repeat=trial_times, # How many trials
        number=1, # Here means run once per trial
    )
    for index, final_time in enumerate(times):
        print(f'Trial{index + 1}: Bubble sort spends {final_time: .6f} seconds to
sort {size} {sample_type}')

```

Optimized Bubble Sort Time Complexity:

```
import copy
```

```

import json

import timeit # it is a python built-in module, it will be used to measure the
average time

#=====Creating a optimized bubble sort
algorithm=====
def bubble_sort(arr):
    n = len(arr)
    for i in range(n - 1):
        flag = False
        for j in range(0, n - i - 1):
            if arr[j] > arr[j + 1]:
                arr[j], arr[j + 1] = arr[j + 1], arr[j]
                flag = True
        if not flag: # flag to track if any swaps occurred in a pass, if no swaps
are needed, it breaks the outer loop.
            break
    return arr

#=====
sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Creating a two dimensional loop for data
testing=====
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:

```

```

filename = f"Sorting samplesample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"

print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine weather the system is executing
#=====Opening the json file=====

with open(filename, 'r') as f:
    data = json.load(f)

new_data = []
for x in data:
    try:
        new_data.append(int(x))
    except ValueError:
        pass # Do ignore non value error...

def run_sort():
    processed_data = list(new_data)
    bubble_sort(processed_data)

#=====Final testing and displaying the result
times = timeit.repeat( #timeit.repeat() runs the same code multiple times and
returns execution times
    stmt=lambda: run_sort(),
    repeat=trial_times, #How many trials
    number=1, # Here means run once per trial,
)
for index, final_time in enumerate(times):
    print(f'Trial{index+1}: Bubble sort spends {final_time: .6f} seconds to
sort {size} {sample_type}')

```

Naive Bubble Sort Space Complexity:

```
# A nice website to learn how to measure the memory usage:
https://parseltongue.co.in/tracking-memory-usage-in-python-with-tracemalloc/#:~:text=Tracking%20Memory%20Usage%20in%20Python%20with%20tracemalloc,memory%20usage.%20*%20tracemalloc.stop():%20Stops%20tracking%20memory.
#https://docs.python.org/3/library/tracemalloc.html

import tracemalloc #A python built-in module to track memory allocations
import json
import time
import copy

#=====Creating a optimized bubble sort algorithm=====
def bubble_sort(arr):
    n = len(arr)
    for i in range(n - 1):
        for j in range(0, n - i - 1):
            if arr[j] > arr[j + 1]:
                arr[j], arr[j + 1] = arr[j + 1], arr[j]
    return arr

#=====

sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5
```

```

def measure_sort_performance(original_data_list):
    processed_data = copy.deepcopy(original_data_list)
    tracemalloc.start() # Start to measure
    start_time = time.perf_counter()
    bubble_sort(processed_data) # run the program
    end = time.perf_counter()
    current_memory, peak_memory = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
    tracemalloc.stop()

    elapse = end - start_time # caculating the elapsed time
    return current_memory, peak_memory, elapse

#=====
#Main:
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting samples/sample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine weather the system is executing
#=====

        with open(filename, 'r') as f:
            data = json.load(f)

        new_data = []
        for x in data:
            try:
                new_data.append(int(x))

```

```

        except ValueError:

            pass # Do ignore non value error...

#=====

    for each in range(trial_times):

        current, peak, elapse = measure_sort_performance(new_data)

        print(f'elapsed time={elapse:.6f}s')

        print(f'{sample_type} {size}: initial memory: {current} bytes')

        print(f'{sample_type} {size}: peak memory: {peak} bytes')

```

Optimized Bubble Sort Space Complexity:

```

# A nice website to learn how to measure the memory usage:
https://parseltongue.co.in/tracking-memory-usage-in-python-with-tracemalloc/#::~text=Tracking%20Memory%20Usage%20in%20Python%20with%20tracemalloc,memory%20usage.%20\*\*%20tracemalloc.stop\(\):%20Stops%20tracking%20memory.
#https://docs.python.org/3/library/tracemalloc.html

import tracemalloc #A python built-in module to track memory allocations
import json
import time
import copy

#=====Creating a optimized bubble sort
algorithm=====

def bubble_sort(arr):

    n = len(arr)

    for i in range(n - 1):

        flag = False

        for j in range(0, n - i - 1):

            if arr[j] > arr[j + 1]:

```

```

        arr[j], arr[j + 1] = arr[j + 1], arr[j]

        flag = True

    if not flag: # flag to track if any swaps occurred in a pass, if no swaas
are needed, it breaks the outer loop.

        break

    return arr

```

```

=====

```

```

sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

```

```

=====

```

```

def measure_sort_performance(original_data_list):
    processed_data = copy.deepcopy(original_data_list)
    tracemalloc.start() # Start to measure
    start_time = time.perf_counter()
    bubble_sort(processed_data) # run the program
    end = time.perf_counter()
    current_memory, peak_memory = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
    tracemalloc.stop()

    elapse = end - start_time # calculating the elapsed time
    return current_memory, peak_memory, elapse

```

```

#=====
#Main:
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting samples/sample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine weather the system is executing
#=====

        with open(filename, 'r') as f:
            data = json.load(f)

new_data = []
for x in data:
    try:
        new_data.append(int(x))
    except ValueError:
        pass # Do ignore non value error...
#=====

for each in range(trial_times):
    current, peak, elapse = measure_sort_performance(new_data)
    print(f'elapsed time={elapse:.6f}s')
    print(f'{sample_type} {size}: initial memory: {current} bytes')
    print(f'{sample_type} {size}: peak memory: {peak} bytes')

```

Quick Sort Time Complexity:

```

import json
import timeit
import random #For selecting a random pivot

```

```

#=====Creating a optimized sort
algorithm=====
# Partition function with randomized pivot
def partition(arr, low, high):
    pivot_index = random.randint(low, high)
    arr[pivot_index], arr[high] = arr[high], arr[pivot_index]
    pivot = arr[high]
    i = low - 1
    for j in range(low, high):
        if arr[j] < pivot:
            i += 1
            arr[i], arr[j] = arr[j], arr[i]
    arr[i + 1], arr[high] = arr[high], arr[i + 1]
    return i + 1

# QuickSort recursive function
def quickSort(arr, low, high):
    if low < high:
        pi = partition(arr, low, high)
        quickSort(arr, low, pi - 1)
        quickSort(arr, pi + 1, high)

def run_sort(new_data):
    processed_data = list(new_data)
    quickSort(processed_data, 0, len(processed_data)-1)

```

```

=====
sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Creating a two dimensional loop for data
testing=====
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting sample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine weather the system is executing
#=====Opening the json file=====

        with open(filename, 'r') as f:
            data = json.load(f)

        new_data = []
        for x in data:
            try:
                new_data.append(int(x))
            except ValueError:
                pass # Do ignore non value error...

#=====Final testing and displaying the result
        times = timeit.repeat( #timeit.repeat() runs the same code multiple times and
returns execution times

            stmt=lambda: run_sort(new_data),
            repeat=trial_times, #How many trials
            number=1, # Here means run once per trial

```



```

return i + 1

# QuickSort recursive function
def quickSort(arr, low, high):
    if low < high:
        pi = partition(arr, low, high)
        quickSort(arr, low, pi - 1)
        quickSort(arr, pi + 1, high)

#=====

sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

def measure_sort_performance(original_data_list):
    processed_data = copy.deepcopy(original_data_list)
    tracemalloc.start() # Start to measure
    start_time = time.perf_counter()
    quickSort(processed_data, 0, len(processed_data)-1)# run the program
    end = time.perf_counter()
    current_memory,peak_memory = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()
    tracemalloc.stop()

    elapse = end - start_time # calculating the elapsed time
    return current_memory,peak_memory,elapse

```

```

#=====
#Main:
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting samplesample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine whether the system is executing
#=====

        with open(filename, 'r') as f:
            data = json.load(f)

new_data = []
for x in data:
    try:
        new_data.append(int(x))
    except ValueError:
        pass # Do ignore non-value error...
#=====

for each in range(trial_times):
    current, peak, elapse = measure_sort_performance(new_data)
    print(f'elapsed time={elapse:.6f}s')
    print(f'{sample_type} {size}: initial memory: {current} bytes')
    print(f'{sample_type} {size}: peak memory: {peak} bytes')

```

Radix Sort Time Complexity:

```

import json
import timeit

```

```

#=====Creating a sort
algorithm=====
#Here is the standard code for radix sort copied from
https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/dsa/radix-sort/

def countingSort(arr, exp1):

    n = len(arr)

    # The output array elements that will have sorted arr
    output = [0] * (n)

    # Initialize count array as 0
    count = [0] * (10)

    # Store count of occurrences in count[]
    for i in range(0, n):
        index = arr[i] // exp1
        count[index % 10] += 1

    # Change count[i] so that count[i] now contains actual
    # position of this digit in the output array
    for i in range(1, 10):
        count[i] += count[i - 1]

    # Build the output array
    i = n - 1
    while i >= 0:

```

```

        index = arr[i] // exp1

        output[count[index % 10] - 1] = arr[i]

        count[index % 10] -= 1

        i -= 1

# Copying the output array to arr[],
# so that arr now contains sorted numbers
i = 0
for i in range(0, len(arr)):
    arr[i] = output[i]

# Method to do Radix Sort

def radixSort(arr):

    # Find the maximum number to know the number of digits
    max1 = max(arr)

    # Do counting sort for every digit. Note that instead
    # of passing digit number, exp is passed. exp is 10^i
    # where i is the current digit number
    exp = 1
    while max1 / exp >= 1:
        countingSort(arr, exp)
        exp *= 10

def run_sort(new_data):
    processed_data = list(new_data)

```

```

radixSort(processed_data)

#=====
sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Creating a two dimensional loop for data
testing=====
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting samplesample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine whether the system is executing
#=====Opening the json file=====
        with open(filename, 'r') as f:
            data = json.load(f)

            new_data = []
            for x in data:
                try:
                    new_data.append(int(x))
                except ValueError:
                    pass # Do ignore non-value error...
#=====Final testing and displaying the result

        times = timeit.repeat( # timeit.repeat() runs the same code multiple times and
returns execution times

```

```

        stmt=lambda: run_sort(new_data),

        # data.copy() is used to make sure that sorting algorithms do not affect
the original data files

        repeat=trial_times, # How many trials

        number=1, # Here means run once per trial

    )

    for index, final_time in enumerate(times):

        print(f'Trial{index + 1}: Radix sort spends {final_time: 6f} seconds to
sort {size} {sample_type}')

```

Radix Sort Space Complexity:

```

import time
import tracemalloc #A python built-in module to track memory allocations
import json
import copy

#=====Creating a optimized sort
algorithm=====
def countingSort(arr, exp1):

    n = len(arr)

    # The output array elements that will have sorted arr
    output = [0] * (n)

    # initialize count array as 0
    count = [0] * (10)

    # Store count of occurrences in count[]

```

```

for i in range(0, n):
    index = arr[i] // exp1
    count[index % 10] += 1

# Change count[i] so that count[i] now contains actual
# position of this digit in output array
for i in range(1, 10):
    count[i] += count[i - 1]

# Build the output array
i = n - 1
while i >= 0:
    index = arr[i] // exp1
    output[count[index % 10] - 1] = arr[i]
    count[index % 10] -= 1
    i -= 1

# Copying the output array to arr[],
# so that arr now contains sorted numbers
i = 0
for i in range(0, len(arr)):
    arr[i] = output[i]

# Method to do Radix Sort

def radixSort(arr):

# Find the maximum number to know the number of digits

```

```

max1 = max(arr)

# Do counting sort for every digit. Note that instead
# of passing digit number, exp is passed. exp is 10^i
# where i is current digit number

exp = 1

while max1 / exp >= 1:

    countingSort(arr, exp)

    exp *= 10

#=====

sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Opening the json file=====

def measure_sort_performance(original_data_list):

    processed_data = copy.deepcopy(original_data_list)

    tracemalloc.start() # Start to measure

    start_time = time.perf_counter()

    radixSort(processed_data)# run the program

    end = time.perf_counter()

    current_memory,peak_memory = tracemalloc.get_traced_memory()

    tracemalloc.stop()

    elapse = end - start_time # caculating the elapsed time

    return current_memory,peak_memory,elapse

```

```

#=====
#Main:
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting samplesample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine whether the system is executing
#=====

        with open(filename, 'r') as f:
            data = json.load(f)

new_data = []
for x in data:
    try:
        new_data.append(int(x))
    except ValueError:
        pass # Do ignore non-value error...
#=====

for each in range(trial_times):
    current, peak, elapse = measure_sort_performance(new_data)
    print(f'elapsed time={elapse:.6f}s')
    print(f'{sample_type} {size}: initial memory: {current} bytes')
    print(f'{sample_type} {size}: peak memory: {peak} bytes')

```

Merge Sort Time Complexity:

```

import json
import timeit

```

```

#-----Creating a sort
algorithm-----
def merge(arr, left, mid, right):
    n1 = mid - left + 1
    n2 = right - mid
    L = [0] * n1
    R = [0] * n2
    for i in range(n1):
        L[i] = arr[left + i]
    for j in range(n2):
        R[j] = arr[mid + 1 + j]
    i = 0
    j = 0
    k = left
    while i < n1 and j < n2:
        if L[i] <= R[j]:
            arr[k] = L[i]
            i += 1
        else:
            arr[k] = R[j]
            j += 1
        k += 1
    while i < n1:
        arr[k] = L[i]
        i += 1
        k += 1
    while j < n2:
        arr[k] = R[j]
        j += 1

```

```

    k += 1

# Merge Sort recursive function
def mergeSort(arr, left, right):
    if left < right:
        mid = (left + right) // 2
        mergeSort(arr, left, mid)
        mergeSort(arr, mid + 1, right)
        merge(arr, left, mid, right)

#=====
def run_sort(new_data):
    processed_data = list(new_data)
    mergeSort(processed_data, 0, len(processed_data)-1)

#=====

sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Creating a two dimensional loop for data
testing=====
for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting sample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine whether the system is executing
#=====Opening the json file=====

```

```

with open(filename, 'r') as f:
    data = json.load(f)

new_data = []

for x in data:
    try:
        new_data.append(int(x))
    except ValueError:
        pass # Do ignore non-value error...

#=====Final testing and displaying the result
times = timeit.repeat( # timeit.repeat() runs the same code multiple times and
returns execution times

    stmt=lambda: run_sort(new_data),
    repeat=trial_times, # How many trials
    number=1, # Here means run once per trial
)

for index, final_time in enumerate(times):
    print(f'Trial{index + 1}: Merge sort spends {final_time: .6f} seconds to
sort {size} {sample_type}')

```

Merge Sort Space Complexity:

```

import json

import timeit

#=====Creating a sort
algorithm=====

```

```

def merge(arr, left, mid, right):

    n1 = mid - left + 1

    n2 = right - mid

    L = [0] * n1

    R = [0] * n2

    for i in range(n1):

        L[i] = arr[left + i]

    for j in range(n2):

        R[j] = arr[mid + 1 + j]

    i = 0

    j = 0

    k = left

    while i < n1 and j < n2:

        if L[i] <= R[j]:

            arr[k] = L[i]

            i += 1

        else:

            arr[k] = R[j]

            j += 1

        k += 1

    while i < n1:

        arr[k] = L[i]

        i += 1

        k += 1

    while j < n2:

        arr[k] = R[j]

        j += 1

        k += 1

```

```

# Merge Sort recursive function
def mergeSort(arr, left, right):
    if left < right:
        mid = (left + right) // 2
        mergeSort(arr, left, mid)
        mergeSort(arr, mid + 1, right)
        merge(arr, left, mid, right)

#=====

def run_sort(new_data):
    processed_data = list(new_data)
    mergeSort(processed_data,0,len(processed_data)-1)

#=====

sample_sizes = [2000, 4000, 6000, 8000, 10000] #size of file to be tested
sample_types = ['random', 'sorted', 'reversed'] # data type
trial_times = 5

#=====Creating a two dimensional loop for data
testing=====

for size in sample_sizes:
    for sample_type in sample_types:
        filename = f"Sorting samplesample_{size}_{sample_type}.json"
        print(f"The system is trying to open: {filename}") # Sending tips for the
experimenter to determine whether the system is executing
#=====Opening the json file=====

    with open(filename, 'r') as f:

```

```

    data = json.load(f)

new_data = []

for x in data:

    try:

        new_data.append(int(x))

    except ValueError:

        pass # Do ignore non-value error...

#=====Final testing and displaying the result

times = timeit.repeat( # timeit.repeat() runs the same code multiple times and
returns execution times

    stmt=lambda: run_sort(new_data),

    repeat=trial_times, # How many trials

    number=5, # Here means run once per trial

)

for index, final_time in enumerate(times):

    print(f'Trial{index + 1}: Merge sort spends {final_time: .6f} seconds to
sort {size} {sample_type}')

```

Create and Save Samples:

```

import random

import pandas as pd # Panda module is used to manipulate, analyze, exploring data

import numpy as np

import json

import os # It is a module used to interact with the operating system

```

```

#===== Specify the data we want=====
data = pd.read_csv('aa.us.txt', engine='python')
numeric_value = data['Volume'].dropna().tolist() # dropna method is used to
handle missing data, tolist() method is used to convert Pandas Series into a standard
Python list

#=====Crating the files=====
output_folder = 'Sorting samples'
if not os.path.exists(output_folder): # os.path.exists() is a function that returns
True or False to check whether the file actually exists or not
    os.makedirs(output_folder) # os.makedirs() is a function to make a
directory(folder)

#=====Creating and saving the sample=====
def create_and_save_samples(data_list, sample_size):
    if sample_size > len(data_list):
        sample_size = len(data_list) # Here is a necessary check to prevent overflow
problem

    sample_data = random.sample(data_list, sample_size)
#=====Create three different data
condition=====
    random_sample_data = sample_data.copy()
    sorted_sample = sorted(sample_data)
    reversed_sample = sorted(sample_data, reverse=True)
#=====Saving each to a separate file=====
    base_filename = f"{output_folder}/sample_{sample_size}"

```

```
with open(f"{base_filename}_random.json", 'w') as f:
    json.dump(random_sample_data, f)

with open(f"{base_filename}_sorted.json", 'w') as f:
    json.dump(sorted_sample, f)

with open(f"{base_filename}_reversed.json", 'w') as f:
    json.dump(reversed_sample, f)

return random_sample_data, sorted_sample, reversed_sample

#Main function:
sample_sizes = [2000,4000,6000,8000,10000]
for size in sample_sizes:
    create_and_save_samples(numeric_value, size
```